

Consumer acceptance and willingness to pay for olive oil with reduced pesticide use in the Euro-Mediterranean region: A reference-dependent contingent valuation approach

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ABSTRACT

While discussions on plant protection product regulations continue within the EU, insights into consumer behaviour regarding the reduction of pesticide use in olive oil production remain limited. This study explores consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) a premium for conventional extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) with 40 % reduced pesticide use across five Mediterranean EU countries. Employing the contingent valuation method—a stated preference experimental approach—with 'payment cards' based on past purchase records, we surveyed 5091 olive oil consumers in France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain using Qualtrics' consumer panels. To analyse the factors influencing both the decision to pay a premium and the premium amount, we applied the Heckman sample selection model, a statistical technique that addresses sample selection bias. The results reveal that 73 % of consumers are willing to pay a premium, with mean premiums ranging from 22 % in Italy to 26 % in France above the reference price for a 1-L bottle of conventional EVOO. Socio-demographic factors—such as age, income, education, and household size—shape the likelihood of paying a premium. Meanwhile, behavioural factors—including knowledge and perceptions of pesticide use—primarily determine the size of the premium. Consumers' age, household income, and previous purchase price also influence the premium amount, although the behavioural factors exert the strongest impact, notably in France, Greece, Portugal, and Spain. These findings offer actionable insights to support the sector's transition to sustainable pesticide use, aligning consumer preferences with the EU's Green Deal objective of halving pesticide use by 2030.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) is the world's leading producer of olive oil, accounting for 55–65 % of the global output, with production concentrated in the southern Mediterranean region [1,2]. Olive oil, particularly extra virgin olive oil (EVOO)—a key element of the Mediterranean diet—has gained global acclaim as a premium cooking oil [3,4]. However, olive oil production is fraught with environmental and social challenges, raising pressing sustainability concerns. Olives are among the most input-intensive crops that are heavily dependent on chemical pesticides and fertilisers to maintain high yields [5,6]. This raises significant concerns regarding human health, biodiversity, and environmental sustainability [7–10].

To address these challenges, the EU has implemented various policies aimed at reducing pesticide use, such as the Pesticide Regulations (EC) No. 1107/2009 and the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (2009/128/EC) in the past [11–13]. Despite these policy measures, pesticide usage in agriculture remains unsustainably high, prompting a new proposal under the Green Deal to halve pesticide use and associated risks by 2030. While this proposal focuses on producers, complementary actions from other stakeholders—particularly consumers—are critical [14]. Research suggests that consumer demand for sustainable products can motivate farmers to adopt environmentally friendly practices [15]. Consequently, understanding consumers' attitudes and willingness to pay (WTP)—the highest price a consumer is willing to spend on a product or service—for products with reduced pesticide use is essential

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for gauging support for the EU Green Deal and encouraging producers to achieve reduction targets.

Modern consumers increasingly prioritise food quality, health benefits, and environmental impacts in their purchasing decisions [16,17]. This shift has spurred significant growth in the demand for healthy, sustainable, and natural products, reshaping market dynamics [18,19]. Attributes such as production methods and naturalness are pivotal in influencing perceptions of value and WTP. For instance, consumers often favour products from sustainable or traditional methods over industrial processes, viewing them as more natural and authentic [20]. Understanding how consumers value different production methods is vital, as their preferences influence sustainable production, policy development, and market strategies.

Despite increasing research on consumer preferences and WTP for sustainable production methods, most studies have focused on organic or other certified practices in relation to pesticide use [21–24]. Furthermore, research on non-organic sustainable food products has largely focused on pesticide-free options, particularly unprocessed items such as fruits and vegetables [25]. This leaves a significant research gap in understanding consumer attitudes toward sustainable conventional practices, such as the reduced use of pesticides—a distinct approach from organic certification—especially for processed products such as olive oil. Bridging this gap is crucial for promoting innovative and sustainable farming technologies that minimise pesticide use and gauging consumer support for the Green Deal targets.

This study seeks to fill this gap by examining consumers' WTP for EVOO with reduced pesticide use. Specifically, it investigates consumers' acceptance of paying a premium for such products, the size of the premium, and the factors influencing these decisions. This research is especially relevant amid ongoing debates over the proposal for the sustainable use of pesticide regulation (SUR) among EU member states. While the immediate implementation of the proposal remains uncertain, positive consumer behaviour regarding pesticide-reduced EVOO, reflected in their WTP, could drive reduction among conventional farmers. In the olive oil sector, for example, this could encourage conventional growers to adopt alternative technologies that reduce pesticide use by up to 40 % in two key ways.

First, higher premiums for pesticide-reduced olive oil could increase farmers' revenues by 9–30 % under average EU market conditions based on the reported premiums for pesticide-free or organic products [25,26]. These increased revenues could help offset the costs of adopting pesticide-reducing technologies. For example, the EU Horizon project, **NOVATERRA**—a project focused on sustainable farming in the Mediterranean olive groves and vineyards—demonstrates that olive growers can implement precision pesticide spraying technologies capable of reducing pesticide use by up to 40 % without compromising pest control efficacy [27]. However, these technologies require an initial investment, which may be passed on to consumers unless subsidised or absorbed within the olive oil production value chain. The determination of consumers' WTP will provide insights into their readiness to support producers' adoption of pesticide-reducing technologies.

Second, consumer preferences significantly influence production practices. If consumers favour extra virgin olive with reduced pesticide use, farmers may be incentivised to adopt more sustainable methods to meet their market demands [28,29]. Thus, this paper provides actionable insights for policy development and marketing strategies, helping to align market dynamics with the EU's sustainability objectives.

The study advances previous methodological frameworks by employing a novel reference price-dependent contingent valuation method (CVM)—a survey-based stated preference technique that elicits people's intended future behaviour in hypothetical markets. Our approach integrates participants' self-reported previous purchase prices as a reference point, enhancing the realism and accuracy of the valuation task. The two-stage Heckman sample selection model—an econometric estimation that supports identifying and mitigating a potential selection bias—is used to identify simultaneously factors influencing

both the likelihood of paying a premium and the magnitude of the premium [30]. Selection bias, which occurs when certain individuals or groups are overrepresented due to specific characteristics, can distort results if unaddressed [31]. By combining these robust methods, the study provides valuable insights into the preferences of olive oil consumers regarding pesticide reduction, highlighting the importance of market-driven incentives in promoting sustainable agriculture.

2. Literature review and background

2.1. Pesticides and their role in agriculture

Pesticides¹ have long been a cornerstone of agricultural practices, significantly increasing productivity and securing global food supplies [32]. Without pesticides, global production is estimated to decline by 78 % for fruits, 54 % for vegetables, and 35 % for cereals [33]. In the EU, research indicates that phasing out pesticide use could lower food production by 3 %–30 %, depending on the crop, with tree crops such as olives, grapes, and apples being the most affected [34,35].

However, extensive pesticide use has severe consequences for the environment and human health, including biodiversity loss, soil degradation, and water pollution [36]. Chronic exposure to pesticides has been linked to health issues such as cancer, neurological disorders, and respiratory problems [9,37].

2.2. Pesticide use in olive cultivation

The olive crop is integral to the socio-economic and cultural fabric of the Euro-Mediterranean region, covering millions of hectares [38]. However, olive cultivation involves substantial use of herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides because of the crop's susceptibility to pests and diseases such as olive fruit flies, moths, and black scales [38]. Euro-Mediterranean countries such as Spain, Italy, and Greece, which dominate olive oil production, report some of the highest pesticide usage in the EU, exacerbating ecological and safety concerns [7,39].

Pesticides applied to soil or olive trees sometimes find their way into olive fruits or surface and ground waters through runoff, percolation, evaporation, and precipitation [40–42]. Monitoring has revealed alarming pesticide contamination levels in surface waters and olive oil, raising environmental and health concerns. A recent study in Spain detected 43 pesticide compounds, including banned substances, in water samples from olive-producing areas, with herbicides and fungicides being the most common contaminants [43]. Similarly, pesticide residues have been identified in extra virgin olive oil, although they are within safe limits for consumption [44]. These findings underscore the excessive reliance on chemical pesticides in olive cultivation, emphasising the need for reduction [9,36].

2.3. Innovative alternatives to reduce pesticide use

Reducing pesticide risk while maintaining productivity requires changes in agricultural practices guided by efficiency [45]. Encouragingly, promising technologies are emerging in the agricultural sector. For example, bacteria such as *Serratia* offer natural pest control through their antimicrobial activity, reducing the need for chemical pesticides [46]. Leveraging plant metabolites to regulate defence responses provides eco-friendly pest management alternatives to chemical fungicides [47]. The use of fungus-resistant varieties, genome-edited crops, and insect-resistant cultivars bred to withstand fruit flies represents cost-effective and sustainable integrated pest management approaches [48–50]. Biological agents, such as symbiotic bacteria, offer promising

¹ Encompasses all compounds that are applied to destroy or regulate plant pests; this includes insecticides (insects), herbicides (weeds) and fungicides (fungi), bactericide(bacteria) and all chemicals used as plant protective products.

environmentally safe pest control tools [38,51].

Furthermore, advancements such as variable rate application—a precision technology based on location-specific qualities—supported by canopy characterisation through satellites and on-board sensors enable precise pesticide application tailored to crop needs, minimising excess application and environmental harm [27,52].

These innovations collectively represent a significant step toward reducing reliance on chemical pesticides while ensuring effective pest control. Nevertheless, their implementation often faces attitudinal, economic, and institutional barriers within the agri-food system, necessitating the need to involve all stakeholders, including consumers [14].

2.4. The role of the consumer in achieving pesticide reduction

The recent EU stringent sustainable pesticide use proposal, driven by policies such as the Green Deal, aims to mitigate the environmental and health risks associated with chemical inputs in agriculture [53]. The targets include a 50 % reduction in chemical pesticide use and increased reliance on integrated pest management (i.e., an environmentally friendly approach to controlling pests that combines multiple strategies to minimise the use of harmful pesticides) by producers [37,53]. However, achieving sustainable pesticide use in agriculture requires collaboration among all stakeholders, including pesticide operators, regulators, researchers, agrochemical and food industries, and consumers [9]. Involving these stakeholders and designing effective policy frameworks are critical to addressing reduction targets [14].

Consumer attitudes and behaviour could be pivotal in achieving EU pesticide reduction targets. Purchasing decisions shape demand for sustainably produced food, as evidenced by the rising popularity of organic and locally sourced products [54,55]. Research underscores that farmers' adoption of eco-friendly practices often depends on economic incentives and external pressures [56]. For this reason, it is suggested that all stakeholders, from the chemical input industry to consumers, be involved in designing appropriate policy frameworks aimed at reducing pesticide use [14]. Furthermore, it has been reported that farmers' adoption of eco-friendly practices is shaped by external factors, such as economic incentives [56]. Consequently, studies have investigated consumer preferences and attitudes toward different sustainable, healthy and novel food attributes to understand how these preferences could be harnessed to promote sustainability [57–60].

The olive oil sector is no exception to studies examining consumer preferences. For example, Zanchini et al. [61] reported that Italian consumers are willing to pay a premium for olive oil enriched with polyphenols, reflecting their preference for health-related benefits. Similarly, research indicates that consumers hold positive attitudes toward olive oil with sustainability labels and are willing to pay more for such products [22]. These findings align with those of Marozzo et al. [62], who found that factors such as sustainability, health benefits, nutritional value, and quality significantly influence consumer behaviour when purchasing olive oil.

Consumer willingness to pay also provides valuable insights for marketing and policy strategies. For instance, Lanfranchi et al. [63] reported that consumers exhibit a greater willingness to pay for organic extra virgin olive oil, which is positively correlated with socio-demographic factors such as older age, higher educational attainment, and smaller household sizes. Such information helps marketers and policymakers target receptive demographics and design strategies that promote organic olive oil products effectively. Furthermore, Katt and Meixner [64] provide a comprehensive overview of consumer-related factors that drive WTP decisions for sustainable products. They include values and attitudes, such as environmental concerns, and behavioural traits, such as purchase frequency, all of which can be leveraged to promote the production of sustainable olive oil [64,65].

Despite the literature exploring consumer preferences and WTP for

different olive oil attributes, there is a notable lack of studies addressing consumer attitudes toward pesticide reduction, particularly in alignment with EU Green Deal targets. While it is well established that consumers generally value sustainability labels, research suggests that consumer motivations may extend beyond these labels [60]. Further, the concept of sustainability often hold different meanings for consumers [22]. This underscores the need to understand how specific sustainability attributes influence consumer decisions, rather than focusing solely on the presence of sustainability labels.

In summary, the EU Green Deal's goal to halve pesticide use by 2030 represents a significant policy effort to promote sustainable food production. However, achieving these targets requires more than farm level regulations. For example, consumer WTP for eco-friendly products, such as pesticide-reduced EVOO, could incentivise producers to adopt emerging pesticide-reducing technologies. To contribute to this, we attempt to answer these critical questions: Are consumers willing to support incremental pesticide reduction targets through their willingness to pay? How much premium are consumers willing to pay for reduced pesticide use, particularly for processed products such as extra virgin olive oil? What factors influence consumer decision regarding their WTP for this product?

3. Research methods

3.1. Product characteristics, study area and data collection

The International Olive Council (IOC) has classified olive oils into eight types based on the oleic acid content and the processing level, although not all of them are suitable for consumption. This study focused on EVOO,² the highest grade of olive oil, which is valued for its low acidity, minimal processing, and superior quality. Unless otherwise specified, references to olive oil in this study refer to extra virgin olive oil, which is the most preferred by consumers due to its premium quality and characteristics. Its growing popularity and high market demand make it an ideal focus for this research, targeting consumers in five major olive oil-producing and olive oil-consuming countries: France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. These EU member states account for 99 % of the Union's olive oil production, with Italy and Spain leading consumption at approximately 500,000 tonnes annually, whereas Greece has the highest per capita consumption at 12 kg per person per year [66].

A nationally representative and demographically balanced sample of olive oil consumers was recruited by Qualtrics©, a market research agency, for the dynamic web-based survey, as explained in Section 3.2. The survey took place between March and May 2023, with the primary requirement being that participants had purchased EVOO within the past three months, as verified through the Qualtrics' European consumer panel database.

A total of 5091 consumers from the five Mediterranean member states consented to participate. Only those aged 18 or older who were primarily responsible for purchasing olive oil for their household were included. Section 4.1 provides further information on the background and characteristics of the participants.

Participation in the survey was voluntary, with no financial incentives provided. Data collection adhered to ethical research standards based on the Helsinki and Belmont declarations, with strict attention to safeguarding anonymity, confidentiality, and privacy in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). All the respondents provided informed consent after receiving a comprehensive overview of the study.

² 'Virgin olive oil which has a free acidity, expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 0.8 grams per 100 grams, and the other characteristics of which correspond to those fixed for this category in the IOC standard'. International Olive Council (IOC). <https://www.internationaloliveoil.org/olive-world/olive-oil/>.

3.2. Survey instrument design

The survey was designed following computer-assisted personal interviewing (CAPI) guidelines that were compatible with both computers and mobile phones. The dynamic platform provided by the Qualtrics® survey tool allows previous responses to be incorporated into subsequent questions in real-time, enabling each consumers' past purchases to serve as a reference for the contingent valuation questions. The survey consisted of three sections. The first section focused on purchasing habits, particularly with regard to the last olive oil purchased for regular home consumption. Only consumers who had bought conventional (non-organic) cooking extra virgin olive oil were included in the analysis, as the study focused on pesticide reduction, which is irrelevant to organic buyer.

The second section focused on the reference-dependent contingent valuation experiment, whereas the third section covered the socio-demographic characteristics, perceptions, opinions, and attitudes of the participants.

To ensure reliable and comparable data across all five countries, the questionnaire was initially designed in English and then translated into the respective national languages by native translators who were also experts in olive oil production. Special attention was given to key terms such as 'pesticides', 'extra virgin olive oil', 'sustainability', and 'conventional' to ensure a clear and consistent understanding across languages.

A pilot survey involving 50 respondents, including some experts, was conducted in each country. Feedback from these pilots was used to refine the final questionnaire before the launch of the actual survey.

3.3. Reference-dependent contingent valuation method

The contingent valuation method was used to estimate consumers' expected WTP for conventional EVOO from alternative innovations that reduce pesticide use by 40%. Contingent valuation is a stated preference method based on individual preferences declared in surveys where a hypothetical market is mimicked [67]. It is a simple and direct elicitation method for evaluating consumer WTP for a product or service [68].

The CVM was selected over other stated preference methods, such as choice experiments, owing to its simplicity and directness in capturing consumer willingness to pay for a single, well-defined attribute such as pesticide reduction. The method is particularly effective for valuing goods perceived as a whole, such as extra virgin olive oil with reduced pesticide use [69]. Unlike choice experiments, which require respondents to trade off multiple attributes, the CVM provides a straightforward valuation in a hypothetical market scenario, making it ideal for products that are not yet commercially available. This ensures clarity and relevance in eliciting consumer preferences, which is consistent with approaches in similar studies prioritising direct valuation for emerging product attributes [70]. Thus, the CVM is preferred for this study for two key reasons. First, the proposed extra virgin olive oil, with 40% reduced pesticide use, is not yet available on the market. More importantly, the study primarily focuses on pesticide reduction as the core sustainability attribute. Consequently, using the CVM enables respondents to directly and easily state their willingness to pay for this specific attribute.

Following a description of alternative innovations capable of reducing pesticide use in olive groves by up to 40%, the respondents were asked directly how much more they were willing to pay for EVOO from these innovations using the price of the standard conventional one that they previously purchased as the starting point. The initial step in the implementation of the contingent valuation method involves creating a hypothetical market for the proposed pesticide-reduced extra virgin olive oil. This is achieved by clearly defining the aim and purpose of the valuation question. Various formats for eliciting WTP have been utilised in the contingent valuation experimental design [71,72]. However, no single format has clear superiority, as its effectiveness

depends on the specific research context.

For this study, the 'payment card' format with price intervals and an open-ended follow-up question was employed because of its advantages. This format combines the benefits of an open-ended follow-up question that captures exact WTP values with those of interval payment cards, which minimises the cognitive burden on participants [73]. Thus, it simultaneously addresses the drawbacks of open-ended formats, reduces protest answers, and mitigates issues associated with dichotomous choice methods and iterative bidding processes, such as the anchoring effect [73,74]. This approach is widely used in the current literature and yields more robust willingness to pay estimates compared to the dichotomous valuation format [30].

Our multiple payment card method involves two-step elicitation questions that are interdependent. In the first question, participants were asked to select among different ranges of values that match the premium they are willing to pay. In the second question, they are asked to specify the exact value given the previous range selected. The price ranges in the first question in relation to the payment cards were left open to allow participants unrestricted choice. Thus, 10 premium price ranges were presented, including zero, which indicates an unwillingness to pay a premium). The option of allowing a zero premium aligns with demand theory and enhances the realism of the valuation task. This approach prevents respondents from feeling compelled to choose from limited, predetermined options, which could bias their preferences [75].

To determine the accurate additional amount that respondents are willing to pay, the price of each respondent's most recent purchase of conventional EVOO was used as the starting point. This starting price in the study is called the reference price, as it serves as the benchmark for determining the premium payment [76].

To incorporate the reference price into the contingent question of each respondent, we employed a dynamic survey technique where previous information gathered from all consumers regarding their previous purchase was once again revealed to them in the contingent valuation question.³ Table 1 below shows a summary of the steps in the contingent valuation task.

Research shows that people tend to overestimate their WTP in hypothetical scenarios because they actually do not have to make real payments. As a result, they may prioritise factors unrelated to cost, leading to a gap between their stated intentions in surveys and their actual behaviour in the market, a phenomenon known as hypothetical bias [77]. To mitigate hypothetical bias, a cheap talk script⁴ and solemn oath⁵ were used at the beginning of the questionnaire as proposed by Carlsson et al. [78]. These techniques help align attitudes and intentions in hypothetical situations more closely with those in real-life scenarios [77]. Participants who declined to take the oath were automatically excluded from the survey.

3.4. Two-stage Heckman sample selection model

To identify the factors influencing the likelihood of agreeing to pay a premium and the premium value, we employed the two-stage Heckman

³ The Contingent valuation question followed a detailed description of pesticide-reducing innovations capable of cutting pesticide use by up to 40% in olive grove compared to current methods.

⁴ **Cheap talk script:** Caution! Studies show that people tend to act differently when they face hypothetical decisions. In other words, there are differences between what people say they will do and what they actually do in real markets. However, for this experiment, we want you to act in the same way that you would do if you had to actually pay for the olive oil and take it home. Please take into account how much you truly want to pay for the olive oil produced from 40% pesticide reduction as opposed to the usual conventional one that you purchase for regular consumption at home.

⁵ **Solemn Oath:** I, the consented participant of this experiment, do swear that during this experiment, I will tell the truth and always provide honest answers. Do you agree to this oath? Yes/No.

Table 1

Summary of steps in the reference-dependent contingent valuation method using payment card format.

Preliminary question	Indicate how much in euros (€) that you paid for a 1-L bottle of conventional EVOO that you last purchased for regular home consumption. Answer: <u>XX</u> €
Contingent valuation question	You indicated that you paid <u>XX</u> € for the 1-litre bottle of EVOO that you last bought for regular consumption. How much <u>more</u> are you willing to pay for the same 1-L bottle of EVOO you mentioned before if it is from the alternative innovation that reduce pesticide use by up to 40 % compared to the current standard practice? Imagine that the extra virgin olive live oil has the same attributes as the one you last purchased.
Extra payment	Nothing more (0) 0-1€ <u>1-2€</u> 2-3€ 3-4€ 4-5€ 5-6€ 6-7€ 7-8€ 8-9€ >9€
Follow-up question	You indicated that you are willing to pay <u>X-X</u> € more. Please state the specific amount you are willing to pay.

sample selection model following Khalil et al. [30]. The use of the Heckman sample selection model is motivated by its ability to minimise sample selection bias in situations, where a significant sample decides against paying a premium. In studies of this nature where the attribute is unknown to some of the consumers in the marketplace, it is expected that a significant proportion will be unwilling to accept to pay a premium, leading to a non-random subsample of consumers who are willing to pay a premium, as demonstrated by studies analysing expenditures on novel product attributes [30,79]. As noted by Phan et al. [80], zero WTP decisions can significantly impact the statistical analysis and modelling. Therefore, using conventional linear regression models such as ordinary least squares (OLS) can lead to biased and inconsistent parameter estimates when dealing with many zero observations [80–82].

The Heckman sample selection model operates as a two-step regression model, which is specifically suitable for datasets with a considerable number of zero observations. Although the Tobit model established by Tobin (1958) attempts to mitigate the potential bias as a result of zero observations, it is considered more restrictive, as it utilises a single equation to explain both participation and expenditure decisions. Thus, it assumes that the same factors influencing the probability of an outcome also determine the magnitude of that outcome [30, 83]. In contrast, the sample selection model [84], also known as the type 2 Tobit model [85], employs two distinct equations. The first equation is a probit regression model (also called the selection equation) that predicts the decision of whether to make a purchase (in this study, whether to pay a premium or not). The selection equation helps to identify the factors that influence the likelihood of deciding to pay a premium and can be written as:

$$Pr(D_i = 1|X_i) = \Phi(X_i\gamma) = \gamma X_i + \mu_i \tag{1}$$

where D_i is a binary indicator for whether an individual is willing to pay extra or not, X_i is a vector of the observed variables of interest, Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, γ is a vector of parameters, and μ_i is the error term. From the estimation of the selection equation, the inverse Mills ratio (λ), which is the ratio of the standard normal density function to the cumulative distribution function, is calculated. The inverse Mills ratio (IMR) serves as the link between the first and second equations.

The second equation, also known as the outcome equation, is a linear regression model that predicts the amount that will be spent when the decision to pay extra is affirmative [82]. It is the main equation of interest and is estimated while including the IMR (λ) as a covariate to correct for sample selection bias as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta X_i + \alpha \lambda_i + \varepsilon_i \tag{2}$$

where Y_i is the outcome variable of interest (size of premium), X_i is a vector of covariates, β is the vector of coefficients for the covariates, α is the coefficient for the IMR, and ε_i is the error term.

The goodness of fit of the Heckman selection model is determined by the significance of the coefficient of the IMR and the measure of the correlation between the errors of the selection and outcome equations, ρ (ρ). The significance of the IMR coefficient indicates the presence of selectivity bias that the model corrects. The significance of the correlation coefficient (ρ) suggests a rejection of the independence of the error terms of the two equations (i.e., $\rho \neq 0$), indicating the presence of

selection bias and suggesting the existence of unobserved factors that increase the probability of selection.

The partial derivative of the selection and outcome equations with respect to a variable of interest gives their marginal effects. These can be evaluated at data points of interest, such as the sample means of the explanatory variables. The marginal effects are classified into three types. The *direct effect* (or marginal effect on the conditional mean) measures the influence of an independent or explanatory variable on the outcome variable, independent of selection bias. The *indirect effect* (or marginal effect on probability) captures the impact of an explanatory variable on the selection variable through the selection process, as represented by the inverse Mills ratio (IMR). Finally, the *total effect* (or marginal effect on the unconditional mean) reflects the combined influence of explanatory variables on the outcome variable, accounting for both the direct and indirect effects [79]. Specifically, the direct effect explains what determines the magnitude of the premium for those who accept to pay a premium, i.e., it measures how the value of the premium changes as a result of a unit change in a particular independent variable holding all other variables constant. The indirect effect explains the binary decision of whether to pay a premium or not. It measures how consumers who initially express unwillingness to pay a premium for a product may begin to pay a premium due to a change in a specific independent variable, *ceteris paribus*. The total effect provides an overall assessment of what determines the size of the premium through an increase (or decrease) in the direct or indirect effect [79].

The econometric estimation of the Heckman sample selection model was performed using NLOGIT 5.0 software and 300 random draws to arrive at the model parameter estimates.

3.4.1. Variable selection

The Heckman sample selection model is estimated with two dependent variables: (1) whether a consumer is willing to pay a premium (yes/no) for the selection equation and (2) the size of the premium (in €) for the outcome equation. The explanatory variables for the selection equation include gender,⁶ education level (the highest level of education attained), employment status, and household size (number of members). For the outcome equation, the explanatory variables are purchase frequency, knowledge of pesticide use (a dummy variable coded as 1 for consumers with medium to high knowledge of pesticide use in olive cultivation and 0 for those with low or no knowledge), and perception of pesticide use (a categorical ranking of how consumers perceive pesticide use in olive cultivation).

Age, income level, and previous purchase price (in €/L) appear in both equations. These variables were selected on the basis of the study’s objectives and a review of the relevant literature on factors influencing consumer willingness to pay for sustainable products [64]. Table 2 provides a summary of the codification of these explanatory variables.

⁶ In this study, we use the term ‘gender’ to refer to participants who identified themselves as male or female, as reported in the survey.

Table 2
Description of variables used in the Heckman sample section model.

Variable	Measurement coding
<i>Selection equation</i>	
Education level	Ordinal: 1–5 (1 = primary, 5 = master’s or above)
Employment status	Dummy: Not working (0); working (1)
Gender	Dummy: Male (1); female (0)
Household size	Total number of persons in the household
Purchase frequency	Number of occasions purchase is made in a year
<i>Outcome equation</i>	
Knowledge of pesticide use	Dummy: No (0); Yes (1)
Perception of pesticide use	Ordinal: 1–5 (0 = None, 5 = Very high)
<i>Both equations</i>	
Age group	Ordinal: 1–5 (1 = 18–24, 5 = 55+ years)
Income level	Ordinal: 1–6 (1 = <1000€, 6=>5000€)
Previous purchase price	Price in €/litre of EVOO last purchased

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics of the background of participants

The summary statistics in [Table 3](#) provide an overview of the

Table 3
Summary statistics of the demographic background of the respondents.

Variable	Category	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
		1013	1018	1021	1021	1018
Gender	Female	51.1 %	51.4 %	50.7 %	51.7 %	50.6 %
	Male	48.9 %	48.6 %	49.3 %	48.3 %	49.4 %
Age categories	18–24 years	11.7 %	9.2 %	9.5 %	9.7 %	9.2 %
	25–34 years	16.2 %	15.8 %	15.1 %	15.6 %	15.9 %
	35–44 years	18.5 %	20.3 %	19.1 %	20.8 %	21.9 %
	45–54 years	19.5 %	21.2 %	22.6 %	20.7 %	21.9 %
	>54 years	34.1 %	33.4 %	33.7 %	33.3 %	31.0 %
Education level	Up to Secondary	7.7 %	25.3 %	10.1 %	11.4 %	21.5 %
	Post-Secondary	42.0 %	19.4 %	53.2 %	39.8 %	28.3 %
	University (Bachelor)	35.5 %	39.4 %	22.3 %	34.1 %	30.1 %
	Master/PhD	14.8 %	15.8 %	14.4 %	14.8 %	20.1 %
Employment	Student	4.6 %	6.5 %	5.8 %	3.8 %	5.2 %
	Unemployed	6.1 %	13.7 %	11.3 %	9.6 %	12.4 %
	Employee	59.1 %	53.3 %	49.4 %	65.5 %	56.7 %
	Business owner	8.3 %	11.6 %	14.1 %	8.1 %	12.0 %
	Retired	19.9 %	12.1 %	14.6 %	9.4 %	10.3 %
	Other (Specify)	1.9 %	2.8 %	4.9 %	3.5 %	3.4 %
Net monthly household income	<1.000 €	9.3 %	41.6 %	16.7 %	42.6 %	17.9 %
	1.000–2.000 €	34.9 %	39.1 %	47.5 %	40.5 %	44.3 %
	2.001–3.000 €	26.9 %	10.0 %	20.3 %	11.7 %	23.7 %
	3.001–4.000 €	13.7 %	2.8 %	5.7 %	2.3 %	6.5 %
	4.001–5.000 €	7.0 %	2.1 %	4.5 %	1.1 %	3.6 %
	>5.000 €	8.1 %	4.5 %	5.3 %	1.9 %	4.0 %
Knowledge of pesticide use in olive groves	No knowledge	36.1 %	29.3 %	23.0 %	36.2 %	34.7 %
	Low level	45.0 %	41.5 %	50.2 %	45.7 %	44.0 %
	Medium level	15.5 %	22.1 %	22.4 %	16.3 %	17.9 %
	High level	3.4 %	7.1 %	4.4 %	1.8 %	3.4 %
Perception of pesticide use in olive groves	Very high	18.8 %	17.4 %	23.8 %	25.8 %	18.7 %
	High	9.4 %	21.9 %	18.5 %	15.7 %	19.8 %
	Moderate	14.7 %	24.2 %	16.7 %	22.6 %	15.4 %
	Low	41.4 %	18.7 %	12.8 %	9.8 %	12.5 %
	None	15.7 %	17.8 %	28.2 %	26.1 %	33.6 %
Purchase frequency	Once in a week	9.7 %	10.8 %	8.9 %	10.3 %	10.6 %
	Once in 2 weeks	20.7 %	22.8 %	23.9 %	21.5 %	22.6 %
	Once in month	36.9 %	34.3 %	35.5 %	37.6 %	38.3 %
	Once in 2 months	14.4 %	11.3 %	15.3 %	13.5 %	10.4 %
	Once in 3 months	11.0 %	12.4 %	9.6 %	10.3 %	9.5 %
	Once in 6 months	5.2 %	6.1 %	4.9 %	4.8 %	5.8 %
	Once in a year	2.1 %	2.3 %	1.9 %	2.0 %	2.8 %
Household size	Minimum	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Average	2.3	2.6	2.5	2.4	2.7
	Maximum	6.0	6.0	7.0	5.0	6.0

participants’ background across the five countries: France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. The data indicate fairly balanced socio-demographic characteristics among participants. Gender distribution is consistent, with approximately equal proportions of males and females across all countries. All the different age groups are well-represented, with most participants falling into the 35–54 and > 54-year categories, which is consistent with typical population structure of consumers who are active buyers. Education levels vary, with Greece having a higher percentage of participants with secondary education, while Italy and France show significant post-secondary or university attainment. Employment status reflects diversity, as employed individuals form the largest group, with notable variations in unemployment and retired participants, reflecting typical working conditions in the EU. Household income patterns highlight economic disparities, with Greece and Portugal reporting a higher proportion of low-income households, whereas Italy and France have a larger share of higher-income households. Additionally, knowledge and perceptions of pesticide use in olive groves, purchase frequency, and household size show natural variation.

Overall, the sample captures regional differences and demographic variations, reflecting its representativeness of the broader population

and its reliability for the study.

4.2. Consumer willingness to pay premiums

The results of the payment card contingent valuation method are summarised in Table 4 and Fig. 1. Overall, 73 % of consumers across the five countries were willing to pay a premium for extra virgin olive oil with reduced pesticide use, whereas 27 % declined. Among the countries, Italian consumers had the highest percentage of positive responses at 79 %, whereas Spanish consumers had the lowest at 67 %. A consistent trend in the range of the premium that respondents are willing to pay was observed across all countries: the percentage of respondents decreased progressively from the '0–1€' range to the '>9€' range, indicating a general preference for lower premium values.

The mean premium for a litre of extra virgin olive oil from innovations that reduce the rate of pesticide use by 40 % was estimated in the second stage of the CVM experiment, where consumers specified their exact willingness to pay in a follow-up question. French consumers reported the highest mean premium at 2.98 €/L, followed by Greece (2.24 €/L), Italy (2.20 €/L), Spain (2.15 €/L), and Portugal (1.88 €/L). These amounts correspond to approximately 26 % of the average reference price for France, 23 % for Greece, 22 % for Italy, 25 % for Portugal, and 24 % for Spain. On average, across all countries, consumers were willing to pay approximately 24 % more for conventional extra virgin olive oil from innovations that reduce pesticide use by up to 40 %.

Of the approximately 27 % who were unwilling to pay a premium for olive oil with reduced pesticide use (Table 4), further investigation was conducted to understand the rationale behind their decision. The outcome is presented in Table 5 below. More than half of the respondents cited the already high price of extra virgin olive oil as the primary reason for their decision. Approximately 17 % indicated insufficient income as the main reason.

Beyond the economic constraints, approximately 14 % of the respondents believe that the farmers or national governments should bear the cost of pesticide reduction. Furthermore, 9 % simply lacked interest in paying a premium, whereas approximately 3 % expressed scepticism about pesticide-reducing innovations. Finally, 2 % did not consider pesticide reduction important, and 1 % stated that they usually purchase organic products, perceiving no need to pay extra for conventional alternatives.

4.3. Results of the Heckman sample selection model

The application of the Heckman sample selection model is justified, as highlighted in the results, as a significant number of consumers reported zero premium in the contingent valuation experiment.

While a pooled model with country-specific interaction terms could have been employed to identify general trends across the five countries, this approach resulted in larger standard errors and wider confidence intervals for the estimated parameters, despite the adequate sample size. These issues are likely attributable to diverse socio-economic

Fig. 1. Trend in the premium that consumers are willing to pay based on the payment cards.

Table 5

Stated reasons of participants who unwilling to pay a premium.

Reasons	Percentage
1. Prices are already too high	54.05 %
2. My income is not enough	16.99 %
3. I am just not interested in paying extra	9.17 %
4. It is the farmers' duty to reduce pesticide use	8.10 %
5. The government must pay for the innovation	6.23 %
6. I do not believe in new alternative innovations	2.56 %
7. Pesticide reduction is not important to me	1.58 %
8. I already buy organic olive oil	1.30 %

backgrounds, regulatory environments, and behavioural factors across countries. For example, Table 4 indicates varying mean reference prices from previous purchases in each country, reflecting distinct price levels. Such variations could influence the magnitude and nature of selection bias in each country. Consequently, a pooled model might fail to adequately capture these nuances, leading to overly generalised conclusions. Therefore, separate models were utilised to account for country-specific selection biases and parameter heterogeneity, ensuring more precise and regionally relevant results.

The measures of goodness of fit for the Heckman sample selection model are detailed in the final section of Table 6. Across all five countries, the likelihood ratio tests—following a chi-square (χ^2) distribution—were statistically significant at the 1 % level. This finding confirms that the selection correction significantly improves model fit, highlighting the presence of selection bias. The correlation coefficient (ρ), which estimates the correlation between the error terms of the selection and outcome equations, also supports the presence of selection bias. The statistically significant, non-zero coefficients of the correlation coefficient: France (1.00), Greece (0.74), Italy (0.98), Portugal (1.00) and Spain (0.96) indicate that the error terms of the two equations are correlated, further confirming the presence of a selection bias.

This observation implies that certain unobserved factors increase the

Table 4

Mean reference price, response to the contingent valuation question, and mean premium.

Country	Mean previous purchase price (ref. price) €/L	% Response to CVM question		Mean premium WTP (€/L)	% Mean premium WTP
		Not willing to a premium (i.e., WTP = 0 €)	Positive WTP (i.e., WTP > 0 €)		
France (n = 983)	11.5	24.9	75.1	2.98	25.9
Greece (n = 986)	9.6	26.4	73.6	2.24	23.3
Italy (n = 983)	9.8	21.0	79.3	2.20	22.4
Portugal (n = 984)	7.4	28.8	71.4	1.88	25.4
Spain (n = 979)	8.9	33.4	66.6	2.15	24.2
Pooled (N=4915)	9.4	26.9	73.1	2.29	24.4

NB: The reference (ref.) price is the last price paid by consumer for conventional extra virgin olive oil purchased.

Table 6
Factors influencing the likelihood of accepting to pay a premium and premium size for a pesticide-reduced EVOO.

Variable	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
<i>Indirect effect (Selection equation)</i>					
Age	0.50*** (0.13)	0.32** (0.14)	0.33** (0.11)	0.22** (0.11)	0.33*** (0.11)
Confidence interval	0.245 ~ 0.76	0.06 ~ 0.59	0.12 ~ 0.15	0.01 ~ 0.43	0.13 ~ 0.54
Gender (Male)	-0.39* (0.20)	-	-0.37** (0.17)	-	-0.52** (0.22)
Confidence interval	-0.78 ~ 0.01	-	-0.70 ~ -0.04	-	-0.95 ~ -0.08
Household income	-0.43*** (0.13)	-	-0.18* (0.10)	-0.28* (0.15)	-0.15* (0.10)
Confidence interval	-0.67 ~ -0.18	-	-0.38 ~ 0.02	-0.58 ~ 0.02	-0.38 ~ 0.02
Education level	0.12* (0.05)	0.09* (0.03)	0.08** (0.04)	-	0.21** (0.04)
Confidence interval	0.02 ~ 0.22	0.03 ~ 0.15	0.01 ~ 0.15	-	0.13 ~ 0.29
Employment status	0.51** (0.23)	-	-	0.56** (0.28)	-
Confidence interval	0.06 ~ 0.96	-	-	0.01 ~ 1.12	-
Purchase frequency	0.05*** (0.01)	0.06*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	-	0.05*** (0.01)
Confidence interval	0.02 ~ 0.08	0.03 ~ 0.08	0.03 ~ 0.06	-	0.02 ~ 0.06
Last purchase price	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.11** (0.03)	-	-	-0.07*** (0.02)
Confidence interval	-0.03 ~ -0.01	-0.17 ~ -0.05	-	-	-0.11 ~ -0.03
<i>Direct effect (Outcome equation)</i>					
Age	-0.60*** (0.20)	-0.35** (0.17)	-0.58*** (0.15)	-0.41*** (0.15)	-0.58*** (0.15)
Confidence interval	-1.00 ~ -0.20	-0.70 ~ -0.01	-0.88 ~ -0.28	-0.70 ~ -0.13	-0.88 ~ -0.28
Household income	0.47** (0.17)	0.65*** (0.14)	0.36*** (0.14)	0.54*** (0.18)	0.34*** (0.14)
Confidence interval	0.05 ~ 0.73	0.38 ~ 0.91	0.09 ~ 0.62	0.02 ~ 0.89	0.09 ~ 0.61
Last purchase price	0.08*** (0.03)	0.18*** (0.03)	0.12*** (0.03)	-	0.10*** (0.03)
Confidence interval	0.02 ~ 0.13	0.13 ~ 0.24	0.07 ~ 0.18	-	0.05 ~ 0.16
Perception of PPP use	-	1.63*** (0.50)	-	1.21*** (0.46)	-
Confidence interval	-	0.12 ~ 2.09	-	0.31 ~ 2.11	-
Knowledge of PPP use	2.51*** (0.74)	1.49*** (0.75)	-	2.30*** (0.70)	2.53*** (0.66)
Confidence interval	1.06 ~ 3.97	1.02 ~ 2.96	-	0.92 ~ 3.68	1.24 ~ 3.83
<i>Total marginal effect</i>					
Age	-0.10** (0.20)	-0.03* (0.02)	-0.25** (0.13)	-0.19*** (0.12)	-0.25*** (0.10)
Confidence interval	-0.49 ~ 0.29	-0.46 ~ 0.40	-0.88 ~ -0.28	-0.70 ~ -0.13	-0.45 ~ -0.05
Household income	-	0.50*** (0.16)	0.17** (0.06)	0.28** (0.14)	0.19*** (0.15)
Confidence interval	-	0.18 ~ 0.82	0.05 ~ 0.28	0.01 ~ 0.55	0.01 ~ 0.36
Previous purchase price	0.06* (0.03)	0.07** (0.06)	-	-	0.03** (0.01)
Confidence interval	-0.02 ~ 0.11	-0.05 ~ 0.19	-	-	0.01 ~ 0.05
<i>Goodness of fit measures</i>					
Chi-squared (χ^2)	75.46***	58.85***	87.37***	46.79***	70.08***

Table 6 (continued)

Variable	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Correlation coefficient (p)	1.00***	0.74**	0.98***	1.00***	0.96**
Inverse Mills ratio (λ)	7.34***	3.41***	3.47***	5.23***	3.91***
Selected sample	746	728	780	703	663

***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1 ⇒ 1 %, 5 % and 10 % significance levels respectively; Standard errors are in parentheses; Blank (-) = not significant at all three significant levels.

probability of selection—in this case, consumers who are willing to pay a premium. The positive correlation coefficients suggest that these unobserved factors are also associated with higher values of the outcome variable (i.e., the premium amount). Additionally, the inverse Mills ratios, which reflect the presence of selection bias addressed by the model, are significant (p < 0.01) in all five cases. Together, these goodness-of-fit measures validate the appropriateness of the Heckman sample selection model for this analysis.

As outlined in Section 3.4, marginal effects—categorised as direct, indirect, and total—were estimated to identify the factors influencing the likelihood of paying a premium and the size of the premium. These effects were calculated at the mean values of the independent variables. The direct effects were derived from consumers included in the outcome equation (i.e., WTP > 0), whereas the indirect effects accounted for the entire sample used in the selection equation (i.e., both those willing and unwilling to pay a premium). For variables present in both the selection and outcome equations, i.e., equations (1) and (2), the total effect is the sum of the direct and indirect effects.

4.3.1. Factors influencing the willingness to pay a premium (indirect effect)

The results in the first segment of Table 6 reveal that socio-demographic factors—age, gender, household income, education level, and employment status—significantly influence the likelihood of paying a premium for olive oil from innovations that reduce pesticide use by up to 40 %. Among these factors, age consistently has a significant positive effect across all five countries studied. For example, moving up one age bracket increases the probability of paying extra by 50 % in France and 22 % in Portugal.

Gender roles also influence decision to pay, with males being less likely to pay a premium in France, Italy, and Spain, where the probability of paying a premium decreases by 39 %, 37 %, and 52 %, respectively. However, the influence of gender is not statistically significant in Greece and Portugal. Household income is negatively correlated with the likelihood of paying a premium in all countries except Greece. In contrast, education level positively impacts the likelihood of paying a premium in all countries except Portugal. Being employment also positively influences the likelihood of paying a premium in France and Portugal out of the five countries.

In addition to socio-demographic factors, purchase frequency and previous purchase price significantly influence consumers' willingness to pay a premium. More frequent buyers are generally more likely to pay a premium, except in Portugal. For instance, a one-unit increase in annual purchases raises the likelihood of paying extra by 5 % in France, Greece, and Spain, and by 6 % in Italy. Conversely, previous purchase prices negatively affect the probability of paying a premium in France, Greece, and Spain, decreasing it by 2 %, 11 %, and 7 %, respectively, for every €1 increase in the price paid previously.

4.3.2. Factors influencing the magnitude of the premium (direct effect)

The second segment of Table 6 shows the direct marginal effects, which measure the impact of the explanatory variables on the magnitude of premium consumers are willing to pay for extra virgin olive oil with reduced pesticide use. Our analysis reveals that age has a negative

and significant correlation with the amount of extra payment that consumers are willing to pay across all five countries. This suggests that older consumers, or those in higher age brackets, are likely to pay a lower premium compared to what younger consumers are willing to pay. For example, moving up one age group decreases the additional amount that consumers are willing to pay by €0.60 in France and €0.35 in Greece.

In contrast, household income is positively correlated with the premium that consumers are willing to pay in all countries, indicating that the premium that consumers are willing to pay for pesticide-reduced extra virgin olive oil increases as their income increases. For instance, a unit increase in household income raises the premium that consumers are willing to pay, ranging from €0.34 in Spain to €0.65 in Greece.

Furthermore, the price of the last purchase positively influences the premium that consumers are willing to pay in all countries except Portugal. Consumers who previously paid more for standard olive oil are more willing to pay a higher premium for pesticide-reduced olive oil. For example, a €1 increase in the previous price paid corresponds to a premium increase of €0.08 in France, €0.18 in Greece, €0.12 in Italy, and €0.10 in Spain.

The results also indicate that consumers with high perceptions of pesticide use activities, as well as those with knowledge of pesticide use in olive cultivation are willing to pay higher premiums in Greece and Portugal. For instance, a one-level increase in the ordinal measure of perception of pesticide use activities in olive groves raises the premium by €1.63 in Greece and €1.21 in Portugal. However, this effect was not significant in the three other countries.

With respect to the knowledge of pesticide use in olive orchards, the results indicate that those with knowledge of pesticide use in olive orchards are willing to pay a higher premium for EVOO with up to 40 % reduced pesticide use than those with no knowledge. This positive correlation is observed in all countries except Italy, with the strongest impact in Spain (€2.53) and the weakest in Greece (€1.49).

4.3.3. Total effect

The total impacts of the variables that appear in both the selection and outcome equations are summarised under the 'total marginal effect' in Table 6. This metric, which combines direct and indirect effects, provides a nuanced view of consumer behaviour regarding pesticide-reduced extra virgin olive oil, revealing contrasting effects of age, household income, and last purchase price on the likelihood of paying extra and the magnitude of the premium.

For example, the total marginal effects of age across the five countries highlight a complex view of consumer decisions about pesticide-reduced EVOO. While increasing age positively influences the likelihood of opting to pay a premium for the product, it negatively impacts the size of the premium. This finding suggests that although older consumers are more likely to pay a premium, they tend to offer lower amounts than younger consumers.

In contrast, household income and the last purchase price have positive total marginal effects. For household income, the positive direct effect on the size of the premium outweighs the negative indirect effect on the likelihood of paying a premium across all five countries. This suggests that while higher-income consumers are less inclined to opt for a premium payment, they are willing to pay significantly more when they do.

Similarly, the total effect of the previous purchase price is positive in France, Greece, and Spain. Thus, consumers who previously paid higher prices are less likely to pay a premium, but those who opt to pay a premium are willing to pay a larger amount.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study provide several insights into consumer preferences and their willingness to pay for extra virgin olive oil with

reduced pesticide use. These insights have significant implications for producers, policymakers, and marketers aiming to promote sustainable pesticide use among conventional olive growers.

5.1. Consumer WTP for extra virgin olive oil with reduced pesticide use

This study reveals that 73 % of consumers across five Euro-Mediterranean countries are willing to pay a premium for extra virgin olive oil from innovative practices that reduce pesticide use by up to 40 %. The significant number of consumers who are willing to pay a premium for this attribute aligns with broader research on consumer behaviour towards products with zero or reduced pesticide levels, which consistently report consumer preference for such items across various countries. For example, studies conducted in the USA, China, Japan, Pakistan, and Germany have all reported that consumers are often willing to pay a premium for pesticide-free food products [25,86–88]. However, while previous studies reveal consumer preference for pesticide-free food products, our findings suggest that olive oil consumers also value incremental pesticide reduction. This finding supports the idea that conventional producers adopting pesticide-reducing technologies can cater to consumer demand without necessarily transitioning fully to organic production.

The mean premium of 24 % over the price of conventional extra virgin olive oil across the five countries, supports previous findings on consumer WTP for sustainability attributes in the food sector, such as Li and Kallas [89], who reported a 29.5 % average premium for sustainable products. However, the lower premium compared with pesticide-free conventional foods (38.3%–93.7 %), as reported by Nitzko et al. [25] reflects consumers' nuanced valuation of partial versus full pesticide reduction measures. These results emphasise a market potential for products positioned between conventional and fully organic or pesticide-free, addressing both consumer demand and practical constraints on organic transitions for producers.

Among the 27 % of consumers unwilling to pay a premium, over 70 % attributed their decision to economic constraints, such as high olive oil prices or low income. Furthermore, 14 % believed that the responsibility of pesticide reduction should be on farmers or governments, whereas 9 % expressed a lack of interest in pesticide reduction, and 2 % dismissed the importance of reducing pesticides altogether. Using the classification criteria established by Frey and Pirscher [90] for identifying protest responses—those in which respondents report zero willingness to pay despite their true valuation being greater than zero—nearly 89 % of these responses qualify as protest responses. Adjusting for the protest responses, the effective proportion of consumers willing to pay a premium for extra virgin olive oil with 40 % fewer pesticides increases to approximately 90 % of the 4915 valid responses included in the analysis. This leaves only approximately 10 % of consumers whose zero premium truly reflects their preferences, a figure consistent with other studies reporting similar rates of disinterest in paying premiums for pesticide-free products such as fresh fruits and vegetables (6.5–11 %), tomatoes (3 %), or favourite food items (17.6 %) [25].

5.2. Factors influencing consumer decision

The Heckman sample selection model reveals key socio-demographic and behavioural factors influencing consumer decisions regarding acceptance to pay a premium and the size of the premium. Considering that the acceptance of paying a premium for an EVOO with a 40 % reduced pesticide use is significantly high (i.e., nearly 90 % when protest responses are accounted for), we focus our discussion on the direct and total effects.

The total marginal effect suggests that younger consumers across all five countries are willing to pay higher premiums for extra virgin olive oil with up to 40 % reduced pesticide use. These findings are consistent with previous studies on consumer preferences and WTP for sustainable

or eco-friendly products. For example, it has been reported that Generation Z (i.e., individuals born between 1997 and 2012) are particularly influential in driving sustainability efforts because they display a strong commitment to fostering a more sustainable world [91]. Our findings suggest that younger consumers show a stronger commitment to pesticide reduction in Mediterranean olive groves, a result that suggests that they are more likely to favour eco-friendly practices than their elderly cohorts, as reported in previous studies [92,93]. However, it is also possible that younger consumers have higher incomes, which gives them greater financial capacity to pay higher premiums, as income level is reported to determine consumer choices [94]. The positive correlation between income and the premium amount seems to lend credence to this reasoning.

The results (total effects) reveal that those with higher incomes are willing to pay higher premiums across all five countries, which is consistent with the literature on the relationship between sustainability behaviour and income. Previous studies report that individuals with higher incomes demonstrate a greater willingness to pay for environmental protection and sustainable products [93,95]. This inclination stems from their greater disposable income, which allows them to allocate more funds toward premium-priced items. The significant positive influence of income on the size of premium for pesticide-reduced EVOO therefore indicates that income is a key socio-economic factor in terms of consumer decision regarding sustainability premiums, as reported in previous studies [96,97].

Furthermore, the total effect results show that consumers who previously paid higher prices for extra virgin olive oil were more willing to pay higher premiums in France, Greece, and Spain. Although unexpected, this observation is reasonable. Consumers often use past purchase prices as benchmarks when evaluating the value of similar products, a cognitive bias known as the anchoring effect [98]. In effect, if a consumer has been exposed to lower prices, they may tend to pay a lower premium than those accustomed to higher prices.

In addition to the socio-demographic factors and previous purchase price, the results (direct effect) also indicate that those who perceive pesticide use as very high (in Greece and Portugal) and those with knowledge of pesticide use in olive cultivation (in all countries except Italy) are willing to pay higher premiums. Notably, where these variables were significant, they exerted the greatest influence on the premium amount compared with all socio-demographic factors and the previous purchase price. The strong positive influence of these two behavioural factors confirms the assertion that soft variables such as perception and subjective environmental knowledge are becoming increasingly relevant in explaining consumption behaviours and the WTP for sustainable products [99].

Interestingly, all three variables under the total effects exert contrasting effects on the likelihood of paying a premium and the size of premium under the direct and indirect effects, respectively. These contrasting effects arise from the distinct dual-stage decision-making process in the Heckman model. The likelihood of paying a premium (indirect effect) reflects consumers' preference for the sustainable pesticide-reduced olive oil, whereas the premium size (direct effect) reflects their financial capacity. For instance, age has a positive indirect effect but a negative direct effect, suggesting that older consumers value the sustainability attribute but may face budget constraints. Household income has a negative indirect effect but a positive direct effect, indicating that higher-income consumers are reluctant to pay a premium but willing to pay more when they opt to pay. Finally, the previous purchase price has a negative indirect effect but a positive direct effect, revealing that consumers accustomed to paying more are less likely to consider a premium for a 40 % pesticide-reduced EVOO but pay higher amounts when they do.

These findings underscore the complexity of general consumer behaviour, where socio-demographic factors influence different stages of the decision-making process in contrasting ways. The varying effects of these variables highlight their distinct impact on consumer

anticipation (i.e., willingness to pay a premium) and the realised outcome (i.e., the size of the premium paid). This underscores the importance of modelling the selection mechanism that governs both the agreement to pay a premium and the amount paid, using the Heckman sample selection method.

5.3. Implications for producers, policymakers and marketers

This study underscores the importance of supporting intermediate sustainability measures such as incremental pesticide reduction. While fully organic certification remains a desirable goal by the EU, incremental steps can help bridge the gap for conventional producers. For example, the average consumers' willingness to pay of 24 % can help offset the costs of adopting emerging pesticide-reducing technologies, such as the variable rate application powered by canopy characterisation using satellite imagery systems [27,52]. This technology, with an estimated annual cost of €1,375, can reduce pesticide use by up to 40 % in olive orchards with full implementation, as ongoing research under the NOVATERRA project indicates [100]. Thus, the premium consumers are willing to pay can serve as a market incentive, enabling olive growers to achieve the 50 % pesticide reduction targets set by the EU Green Deal with minimal financial burden.

However, the lack of certifications or eco-labels that emphasise the rate of pesticide use in agricultural production limits the ability of producers to differentiate their products. Existing sustainability labels such as protected designation of origin (PDO) and organic certification schemes focus primarily on origin and chemical pesticide-free attributes, respectively, leaving a gap for intermediate products that do not qualify for such certifications. Policymakers could consider developing new or integrating pesticide use metrics into established eco-labels. Such metrics could help communicate pesticide footprints effectively, enabling consumers to make informed choices while rewarding farmers' efforts.

The identified determinants of consumers' willingness to pay provide actionable insights for market segmentation and targeted campaigns. Younger consumers, high-income households, and those with greater environmental awareness represent prime targets. Campaigns emphasising the health concerns of pesticide use and the environmental benefits of pesticide reduction, coupled with transparent labelling, could resonate with segments of olive oil consumers who value pesticide reduction.

5.4. Barriers to practical implementation and solutions

While the study highlights consumers' willingness to pay a premium for pesticide-reduced olive oils, several challenges may hinder actual purchase decisions. The COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war have significantly increased food prices, particularly for sunflower and olive oils, raising global concerns, including in Europe [101]. The FAO has reported a 17.1 % rise in the Food Price Index (FPI) following these crises [102], which has already strained consumers' purchasing power [103]. These economic pressures make premium pricing for sustainably produced products, such as pesticide-reduced olive oil, a substantial barrier for price-sensitive buyers.

Consumers often express their willingness to pay for sustainability in hypothetical scenarios, but real market constraints such as rising food costs can limit actual purchasing decisions, especially for low-income households [104]. This could create a gap between positive attitudes and actual behaviour commonly referred to as the attitude-behaviour gap [105]. To avoid pricing pesticide-reduced extra virgin olive oil out of reach of consumers, producers must set premiums carefully and reasonably to align the expressed willingness to pay with affordability.

Other barriers, such as limited availability, lack of consumer knowledge, and insufficient information about pesticide use in olive production, could also hinder the acceptance of these products [106, 107].

Addressing these challenges requires market interventions that

balance consumer affordability with producers' economic viability. Subsidies or financial incentives could help close the price gap between pesticide-reduced and conventionally produced olive oils. A collaborative effort among stakeholders is essential to promote pesticide-reduced extra virgin olive oil among consumers by ensuring affordability and accessibility for all.

5.5. Limitations and future research

Despite achieving its objectives, the study has few limitations worth highlighting. First, it focuses specifically on consumers in the Euro-Mediterranean region, which may restrict the generalisability of its findings to other EU Member States with different cultural and economic contexts. The premium for EVOO with 40 % reduced pesticide use could differ significantly in other regions, leaving room for future studies to broaden the scope across other EU member states.

Additionally, while the study employed mitigation strategies such as the 'cheap talk' and 'solemn oath' scripts to reduce biases inherent in stated preference studies, it is important to acknowledge the potential for residual biases. Social desirability bias may still creep into participants' self-reported choices, as they may provide responses they perceive as socially acceptable or desirable [108]. For example, consumers might overstate their willingness to pay for reduced pesticide use to align with perceived societal expectations of environmentally conscious behaviour. This overstatement could result in discrepancies between stated preferences and actual purchasing behaviour, which should be considered when interpreting the findings.

Subsequent studies could take additional steps to address residual bias by quantifying its extent, such as validating responses against external benchmarks or employing techniques such as indirect questioning or additional questions to determine a respondent's person-specific social desirability bias, which can be used as a correction factor [109]. Such measures would enhance the robustness of future analyses of consumer preferences in studies using stated preference methods. Moreover, future research could expand on this study by introducing additional attributes of extra virgin olive and use other stated-preference methods, such as the discrete choice experiment, to capture the specific value consumers place on pesticide reduction relative to other quality or sustainability attributes.

6. Conclusion

This study provides important insights into consumer behaviour regarding pesticide reduction in olive cultivation by exploring their willingness to pay a premium for extra virgin olive oil with reduced pesticides, the size of the premium and the factors influencing their decisions. The findings highlight strong consumer support, with over 73 % of respondents willing to pay a premium and an average WTP of 24 % for extra virgin olive oils from technologies that reduce pesticide application rate by 40 % compared to standard conventional methods.

Consumers' decisions regarding premium payment are shaped by socio-demographic factors such as age, income, and prior purchase price, alongside behavioural factors such as knowledge of pesticide use and perceptions of pesticide use activities in olive groves. These findings highlight opportunities to leverage market-driven incentives to promote environmental sustainability in the Mediterranean olive sector.

For producers, adopting pesticide-reducing technologies could unlock economic and environmental benefits, supported by consumer premiums. Policymakers could further incentivise this transition by integrating pesticide footprint metrics into existing certification schemes or consider new eco-labels based on pesticide footprints for sustainable conventional products. These measures could help bridge the gap between conventional and organic olive oil, encouraging the gradual adoption of pesticide-free practices among producers.

For consumers, transparent labelling, which includes information on pesticide usage at the farm level, can foster trust and empower informed

purchasing decisions. Marketers can target younger, higher-income demographics with sustainability campaigns, amplifying the benefits of extra virgin olive oils from pesticide-reducing technologies.

Finally, the findings support the EU Green Deal goals, which broadly align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, including responsible consumption, economic growth, and environmental protection. The results suggest the sector can leverage consumer-driven incentives to promote pesticide reduction in olive production. By meeting consumer demands while implementing smart policies and market strategies, the sector can create a win-win solutions that benefit everyone involved in the olive oil value chain—from producers to consumers and the environment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Noah Larvoe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Yasmina Baba:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Zein Kallas:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Felicidad De Herralde:** Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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